

D1.8

Report on cluster collaboration

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Deliverable abstract

The report summarises the collaboration between the environmental research infrastructures cluster and other ESFRI clusters during the conduction of the project.

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Main Author	Andreas Petzold	FZJ	29-06-2023
Contributing Authors	Anca Hienola	FMI	
Reviewer(s)	Katrin Seemeyer	FZJ	29-06-2023
Approver	Andrea Petzold	FZJ	30-06-2023

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DOCUMENT AMENDMENT PROCEDURE

Amendments, comments and suggestions should be sent to the Project Manager at manager@envri-fair.eu.

GLOSSARY

A relevant project glossary is included in Appendix A. The latest version of the master list of the glossary is available at <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4471374>.

PROJECT SUMMARY

ENVRI-FAIR is the connection of the ESFRI Cluster of Environmental Research Infrastructures (ENVRI) to the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC). Participating research infrastructures (RI) of the environmental domain cover the subdomains Atmosphere, Marine, Solid Earth and Biodiversity / Ecosystems and thus the Earth system in its full complexity.

The overarching goal is that at the end of the proposed project, all participating RIs have built a set of FAIR data services which enhances the efficiency and productivity of researchers, supports innovation, enables data- and knowledge-based decisions, and connects the ENVRI Cluster to the EOSC.

This goal is reached by: (1) well defined community policies and standards on all steps of the data life cycle, aligned with the wider European policies, as well as with international developments; (2) each participating RI will have sustainable, transparent, and auditable data services, for each step of data life cycle, compliant to the FAIR principles. (3) the focus of the proposed work is put on the implementation of prototypes for testing pre-production services at each RI; the catalogue of prepared services is defined for each RI independently, depending on the maturity of the involved RIs; (4) the complete set of thematic data services and tools provided by the ENVRI cluster is exposed under the EOSC catalogue of services.

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D1.8 – Report on cluster collaboration

1 Introduction

The Science Clusters have grown out of five collaborative projects funded by the European Union in 2019 to link ESFRI and other world-class Research Infrastructures (RIs) to the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC). The Science Clusters cover today environmental sciences (ENVRI-FAIR), life sciences (EOSC-Life), astronomy and particle physics (ESCAPE), photon and neutron sciences (PANOSC), and social sciences and humanities (SSHOC). They ensure strong connections between Research Infrastructures on the ESFRI Roadmap, between the Science Clusters themselves and jointly towards the EOSC. They are also seen as key for the transitioning of ESFRI RIs from servicing only their communities towards more integrated services in response to the Grand Challenges and transforming their research products for economic and societal users.

The services developed by the clusters and other outcomes of the projects are cornerstones of the emerging EOSC fabric and support both disciplinary communities and multidisciplinary initiatives with harmonised models for access to data, tools, workflows, and training. Each cluster unites multiple RIs in their specific scientific domain.

In recognition of their multiple roles in the ESFRI - EOSC landscape and to advance the related tasks, the Science Clusters have established an intense collaboration on several fields and started regular meetings of the group of ESFRI science cluster projects coordinators. Particularly, the group of Science Cluster coordinators developed into the main point of contact for the European Commission, ESFRI, EOSC Association, and ERIC forum, when it comes to topics of interest for all Science Clusters, independent of their specific research fields, expertise, and communities.

2 Joint Outputs

Although the five ESFRI RI cluster projects span a broad range of scientific fields - from life sciences and environmental sciences through social sciences and humanities to photon and neutron sciences, and astronomy and particle physics - the expectations, needs and offers from the clusters point of view towards the EOSC are very similar and developed into a common view on the EOSC. From the ESFRI cluster projects perspective EOSC is built from three levels: E-Infrastructure consolidation plus Open science plus Scientific Communities' content and users, as illustrated in Figure 1.

Figure 1. ESFRI thematic cluster view on EOSC (Blomberg and Petzold, 2020)

Science Cluster coordination activities span multiple levels:

- Science clusters coordinate their contributions to the EOSC Symposia to ensure as broad as possible communication of science-related requirements and contributions to EOSC and to help shaping EOSC also for the needs of the different scientific communities.
- On the technical level, Science Cluster projects align technical developments and invite representatives of each cluster to annual meetings, thus streamlining the cluster projects workflows, and ensuring coherence of results provided by the cluster projects to EOSC.
- On the communication level, the communication officers of the ESFRI cluster projects established regular meetings to coordinate communication on topics of relevance for all cluster projects and to develop communication resources which can be used by all Science Clusters.

As part of their strategic actions, the Science Clusters have released several important documents to articulate their joint vision and contribute to the development of the EOSC and their aspirations for its implementation.

As such, having in mind that the EOSC initiative has had a significant impact on structured access to Open Data (and with current funding from the European Commission, the interdisciplinary utilization of data is expected to improve further) a compilation of five position papers from ESFRI cluster projects (Goetz et al., 2019), collected by the EOSCsecretariat.eu project, aimed to contribute to the development and implementation process of EOSC. The papers highlight the research community's expectations, the added value of EOSC, issues to be addressed by the EOSC executive board, and commitments to EOSC. The projects expect EOSC to enhance data accessibility and reusability, increase the scientific value of research data, and provide an interoperable environment for data infrastructures. The common recommendations of the projects include the need for clear communication about EOSC, the definition of a common standard for FAIR data, a research community-centred approach, a long-term open data archive, the provision of essential services, collaboration with publishers, cost-benefit analysis, guidelines for joining and using EOSC services, and positioning the business model of the Federating Core at the national level.

Furthermore, the Science Clusters have undertaken a significant endeavour by publishing in June 2021 a comprehensive white paper that addresses the clusters' position in the field of Open Science (Lamanna et al., 2021). This document summarizes various aspects, including the current developments and future plans of each cluster, as well as the collective actions and potential directions they envision. To disseminate this information effectively, a targeted virtual information event was organized, with specific stakeholders such as the EOSC Association, ESFRI, and the European Commission in attendance.

The creation of the second position statement document was a result of extensive interactions between the science clusters, the European Commission, the EOSC Association, and the governing bodies of the ESFRI RI partners. It was developed through continuous collaboration among the management boards of the five science cluster projects over the years. This comprehensive document was collectively presented to the broader community during the stakeholder engagement event titled "ESFRI Science Clusters' Long-Term Commitments to Open Science"^[1] on 1 June 2021.

Recognizing the importance of their collective voice, the clusters have also issued a common statement to the EOSC Association (Annex 1). This statement was intended to contribute to the preparation of their response to the content of the next Work Programme, highlighting key future perspectives and priorities identified by the clusters. In short, the statement highlights the Science Clusters work towards addressing the fragmented research data landscape by promoting open science and contributing to the development of dedicated FAIR services, their support for the implementation of EOSC, improvement of metadata and data quality, widen outreach, and the sustainability of EOSC. The Science Clusters' expected impacts include evolving as platforms for scientific interoperability, advancing FAIR stewardship and innovation of scientific software, creating an open innovation environment, and developing a sustainable model for EOSC science communities. Collaboration with the EOSC Association is sought to address fragmentation and limited impact, support sustainable policies and services, and establish frameworks for rewarding scientists and supporting careers.

^[1] <https://eosc-portal.eu/events/esfri-science-clusters-long-term-commitments-open-science>

The ESFRI Science Clusters together with European e-infrastructures, as being committed to contributing to EOSC's success, released a common declaration (Appleton et al., 2020), calling for a re-orientation of EOSC activities towards higher relevance for the scientific communities. Efforts should now focus on user adoption, making EOSC user-centric and ensuring research-oriented services, trust-based open access, collaboration support, and sustainability.

Furthermore, in December 2021, each cluster was requested to create "Project briefs" to support the forthcoming Horizon Europe (HE) program and policy initiatives during the period of 2023-2024. These briefs aimed to address internal advancements in relation to five key areas of interest for the European Commission. Specifically, they focused on highlighting the primary achievements to date, anticipated developments by the project's conclusion, and recommendations and priorities for future engagement related to the ongoing evolution of the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC). The areas of interest included integration with EOSC infrastructure, implementation of FAIR principles and repositories, technical, semantic, legal, and organizational interoperability, data stewardship, and cross-cluster collaboration. These project briefs were intended to contribute to the HE programme and policy activities and provide valuable insights for the future of EOSC.

The ENVRI-FAIR Project Brief (Adamaki et al., 2021) provides a comprehensive overview of the strategic advancements made in the ENVRI-FAIR Science Cluster project to promote interoperability among its research infrastructures and highlights the current state of interactions at the Science Cluster level. While significant progress has been achieved, it is important to acknowledge that the report represents an ongoing effort. Although the implementation of FAIR principles will reach a promising level of maturity by the end of ENVRI-FAIR, it is recognized that individual RIs still have work to do in achieving full FAIRness, requiring dedicated resources at the RI level. This includes not only advancing the implementation of FAIR-enabling resources but also developing cross-RI services that promote interoperability based on scientific collaboration. Furthermore, the continued development of the ENVRI-Hub as the collaborative platform within EOSC will necessitate additional resources at the ENVRI cluster level to transform it into a fully functional EOSC portal for the Environmental Research Infrastructure ecosystem.

Lastly, the clusters coordinated their viewpoints through individual responses, such as the meeting between the EOSC Association Board and the ongoing H2020 INFRAEOSC projects on 8th April 2022. This was followed by a survey to identify key exploitable results, with a deadline of 1st May 2022.

3 Cross-Cluster Events

The science clusters have been actively participating in the recent editions of the EOSC Symposium where they have had the opportunity to share their achievements, discuss best practices, and exchange ideas with fellow researchers, policymakers, and stakeholders in the field of open science. Their presentations have shed light on the innovative approaches, methodologies, and technologies being employed to enhance the accessibility, interoperability, and reusability of research data within the EOSC framework. Additionally, the science clusters have shared their vision for the future of EOSC, outlining their strategic plans and goals for further progressing the initiative in the next stages.

Within the context of RDA plenaries, two collaborative events were arranged, bringing together representatives from the five cluster projects. These gatherings focused on exploring shared areas of interest, such as community research data management solutions, thematic data services, engagement with end-user communities, and governance.

During the 14th Plenary meeting of the Research Data Alliance in Helsinki in October 2019, SSHOC organized a workshop titled "**EOSC. ESFRI cluster projects. RDA. Connecting commonalities and collaborative solutions for community research data services.**" The workshop aimed to foster discussions and collaboration among representatives from EOSC, ESFRI cluster projects, and RDA Working and Interest Groups. The outcomes of the event were documented in a report (Dekker et al., 2019).

After a year and a half since the Helsinki session, the five ESFRI cluster projects, along with representatives from the RDA community and the EOSC, reconvened to discuss their collaboration in integrating thematic services into EOSC. The event entitled "**The ESFRI Clusters at RDA House of**

Commons," was organized by SSHOC and held as a co-located event during the 17th RDA Plenary meeting on 19 April 2021 ^[2].

The discussions focused on three key topics: thematic data services, connecting to end-user communities, and governance, with the aim of exploring commonalities and fostering collaboration among the ESFRI cluster projects (<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5024589>). To gather input from various stakeholder groups, including the international RDA community, the ESFRI community, the EOSC ecosystem, and domain researchers as the end-user community, the ESFRI cluster projects engaged members of these groups in the debating team and actively involved the audience in the discussions.

4 Other Collaborative Initiatives

In addition to the aforementioned events and activities focused on cross-cluster collaboration to advance the construction of EOSC, the clusters utilized several other platforms for exchanging information and ideas:

- The **ERIC Forum** (<https://www.eric-forum.eu/>) is an initiative that aims to enhance the functioning of ERICs and play a strategic role in shaping policies related to ERICs. The governance structure of the ERIC Forum ensures that each of the five ESFRI clusters is properly represented, with an executive board position dedicated to each cluster. This setup facilitates timely discussions on topics and issues of mutual interest, including those related to the broader landscape of research infrastructures, including EOSC.
- The **EOSC and ESFRI Interest Group** (<https://www.eoscsecretariat.eu/communities/EOSC-ESFRI>) was established in July 2020 to facilitate information sharing among the ESFRI cluster projects and enable discussions on the Strategic Research and Innovation Agenda (SRIA). The group included representatives from the EOSC Secretariat project. The IG focused on various technical topics such as avoiding duplication, enhancing knowledge of existing platforms, creating use cases, identifying hidden opportunities within the clusters, linking technical advancements in the clusters with EOSC, discussing interoperability and cataloguing, and providing feedback to the EOSC Working Groups on the utilization of deliverables.

The fourth level of activities within the Science Clusters focused on supporting project interoperability and facilitating collaboration between the clusters. One aspect of this activity was the sharing of information regarding the direction and main achievements of each cluster's projects. This allowed the clusters to exchange knowledge and experiences, promoting a collaborative approach to their work.

To facilitate this knowledge sharing, a practical virtual workshop was organized in December 2020. The workshop specifically addressed the use of Jupyter and other shared notebook environments, which are popular tools for collaborative coding and data analysis. By providing training and guidance on these tools, the clusters aimed to enhance their members' capabilities in working together effectively.

Furthermore, the clusters also shared their own development plans and progress reports during this period and identified areas of common interest and explore opportunities for further collaboration and coordination, including discussions on the continuation of joint actions even after the projects' official end dates.

As a result of the Horizon Results Booster (HRB), an initiative promoted by the European Commission, the five clusters have come together to establish a shared website ^[3]. This website serves as an interactive platform where the clusters can collectively exhibit exemplary practices and tangible outcomes derived from their combined efforts. It provides a space to showcase the valuable results achieved through their collaboration, fostering knowledge sharing and highlighting the impact of their collective work.

^[2] <https://eosc-portal.eu/news-and-events/events/esfri-clusters-rda-house-commons>

^[3] <https://science-clusters.eu/>

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6 Annex 1 - Science Clusters Input to EOSC Association

Authors:

ENVRI-FAIR - Andreas Petzold, Ari Asmi

EOSC-Life - Niklas Blomberg, Michael Raess

ESCAPE - Giovanni Lamanna, Ian Bird

PaNOSC - Andrew Götz, Rudolf Dimper

SSHOC - Ron Dekker, Ivana Ilijasic-Versic

Object: Science Cluster inputs to the EOSC Association for the INFRAEOSC destination in the next RI Work Programme (2023-2024).

Title: “Fostering Open Science with Science Clusters of ESFRI research infrastructures through both community-based and interdisciplinary projects and common actions”

Expected goals:

Implementation of EOSC

- Addressing the scientific needs for additional services, interoperability and alignment

Metadata and Data Quality

- Transversal actions towards FAIR stewardship and continued innovation of scientific software

Widening and Outreach

- Open innovation environment for research data, knowledge and services with engaged stakeholders and organisations

Sustaining EOSC

- A sustainable model for science communities to contribute to the EOSC

Preamble

Current landscape.

Research Infrastructures such as the ones on the ESFRI roadmap, are characterised by significant volumes of data they generate and handle. Thousands of researchers across scientific disciplines and other potential users are interested to use these data via Open Access policies. Data-intensive research, and effective data preservation for immediate and future sharing and re-use, are fundamental components of ESFRI projects and landmarks, contributing to their increasing role in responding to societal challenges such as climate change or global pandemics. Before the advent of the Science Clusters, researchers were confronted with a highly fragmented research data landscape and cooperation among ESFRI research infrastructures was community based, with limited scope and focus. The Science Clusters, namely ENVRI-FAIR, EOSC-Life, ESCAPE, PaNOSC and SSHOC, of ESFRI and other pan-European research infrastructures, are successfully helping to address the current situation. They are working with the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC), actively contributing to the setting up of dedicated FAIR services, and promoting practice for open science.

The Science Clusters today ensure strong connections between research infrastructures on the ESFRI Roadmap, between the Science Clusters themselves and jointly towards the EOSC. They are also seen as key for the transitioning of ESFRI RIs from servicing only their communities towards more integrated services in response to the Grand Challenges, and transforming their research products for economic and societal users. In addition, Science Clusters have anticipated the need for interdomain shared views for the benefit of EOSC and excellent science in Europe. They are therefore collaborating,

through regular meetings, and have produced common position papers, co-organised workshops and planned operative trans-disciplinary work programmes. Today the Science Clusters are an integral part of the EOSC, contributing to its development and implementation process, while their services and project outcomes are now forming pillars of the emerging EOSC fabric and contribute significantly to the content of EOSC. As important partners of EOSC, Science Clusters stimulate Open Science practices, cross-domain interoperability, and coordination of the scientific communities, and connecting the numerous Universities and national research institutes concerned by the ESFRI projects' partnership within each cluster.

The next phase.

In the Horizon Europe work programme, the Science Clusters are encouraged by both their own partner ESFRI research infrastructures, as well as by the relevant national institutes, to strengthen their mission in enhancing the participation of science communities by structuring and implementing European Open Data Commons.

The connection between EOSC and the Science Clusters aims to fill the EOSC Exchange with data and services and focus on interoperability. They also work maintaining and reinforcing the connection with corresponding domain-based research consortia and scientists committed to open science. Future projects should aim to support strengthening and advancing the current Science Clusters' roles of "developers", "aggregators" and "integrators" of data services and community-based projects for open science and innovation. Such projects would leverage crosscutting and cross-domain science, potentially connected with European sectoral data spaces¹, where scientific publications and major discoveries are linked to accessible digital objects for reproducible workflows; providing training, committing to education, and engaging citizens in science.

Upcoming proposals within Horizon Europe need to further address the stewardship of digital objects from research infrastructures, and build on previous and current developments of the ESFRI Science Clusters. This means engaging with new communities (even globally), and new projects that have been included in the recently updated ESFRI roadmap², in order to accelerate the uptake of these best practices more broadly. The next actions should include the integration of ESFRI Science Clusters' major thematic services as part of EOSC for domain-specific data management as well as the final implementation, support and operation of open-science virtual research environments for depositing, curating, and analysing data. In many areas, such VREs are expected to be created from the user communities, and the role of the Science Cluster is to build the infrastructure and services to support such activities.

The Science Clusters, meanwhile, are looking forward to collaborating with the EOSC Association. The five major topics³ addressed by the EOSC Association through established dedicated task forces have the consideration of the Science Clusters. Furthermore, such a collaboration would target in particular subjects in which the ESFRI research infrastructures can address the current fragmentation and/or limited impact such as: solutions for sustainable policies and services, schemes for credit systems and frameworks for rewarding scientists and supporting careers.

¹ Health, Industrial and Manufacturing, Agriculture, Finance, Mobility, Green Deal, Energy, Public Administration, Skills

² <https://www.esfri.eu/esfri-roadmap-2021>

³ Implementation of EOSC, Technical challenges on EOSC, Metadata and data quality, Research careers and curricula, Sustaining EOSC.

Expected Impacts

1. The five ESFRI Science Clusters within the EOSC will continue to evolve, driven by the growing scientific need for intra-domain interoperability and alignment. While there will remain organisational diversity between the clusters building on the established federations of domain based (ESFRI or other world-class) research infrastructures, there are common needs within for a collaborative work programme to the benefit of the research communities.

Science Clusters as platforms for scientific interoperability in EOSC will extend on a longer term, either via cluster Consortium Agreements, or by leveraging the existing domain management boards to sustain their commitment in supporting the cross-fertilization, co-development and operation of the developed open-science resources, including thematic virtual research environments. This will ensure that the individual and collective RI data resources, computational and workflow services are exposed, connected and operated within the EOSC.

A dedicated “destination action” aimed at supporting the Science Clusters to their longer-term platform evolution would foster transnational cooperation. It will facilitate the sustainable cooperation among ESFRI projects and support the ESFRI science Clusters for their long-term collaboration.

2. In line with the objectives of Open Science, the five Science Clusters need to structure a specific transversal action towards FAIR stewardship and continued innovation (and legacy) of scientific software. Coordinated activities among the five Science Clusters would enable new and interdisciplinary research, leading to new insights and innovation for science and for society at large, committing research communities, Universities, and Institutes to a federated activity for training and skills development schemes.
 - Encourage collaborative development and operation of common infrastructures, tools and methods for research software, best practices, techniques, and technologies, where appropriate and useful to the research infrastructures, and in accordance with the FAIR principles.
 - Cross-cluster collaboration and cross-fertilization/synergies between the RI's and with academia and industry on new digital technologies and tools based on exa-scale data management (Artificial Intelligence/Machine Learning, Quantum Computing, Real-time/Edge Computing Data workflows etc.) with a new focus on education and training by research programmes facilitating early career development of new generations.
 - Support research software collaboration across Science Clusters, technology interest groups/foundations, while leveraging existing international initiatives and encouraging national efforts from many countries on developing open-source solutions.
 - Organize a regular conference series on broad cross-domain Scientific Computing covering all aspects and building on existing domain- and technology specific conferences (e.g. CHEP, HPC).

A dedicated structuring action within the next HE work programme is needed to realise this impact. It will leverage the current achievements of the Science Clusters and enhance the inter-domain potential for excellent science in Europe. The Science Clusters are ready to work with emerging national initiatives on data-intensive science to structure further the European part of a global coordinated effort.

3. Contribute to the creation of a cross-border and multi-disciplinary open innovation environment for research data, knowledge and services with engaged stakeholders and organisations.

- Support and help new research infrastructures develop and integrate with the EOSC multi-cluster ecosystem and collaborate with the EOSC Association. This activity would include mostly ESFRI roadmap infrastructures, but could also include key Member State run national infrastructures of international importance and use.
- Ensure cooperation of research infrastructure-specific and national platforms with EOSC; this could be synergistic and build on common developments and tools, or foster coexistence and collaboration. It can also stimulate a level-playing field within Europe.
- Leverage multi-domain data and a large spectrum of digital objects populating the main European Data Spaces to incentivize some explorative cross-cluster and cross-border open challenges for science, economy, technology, and society.
- Support the Science Cluster role in operationalising the European Research Area (ERA). Organise dialogue, share strategy with ERICs and other research infrastructures for a better link to governance of ERA aiming at matching policy priorities with needs of ERICs' operation and their exploitation by the scientific communities.
- Commit in a structured action in support of a stable Citizen-Science programme around missions for the exploitation of digital objects from the ESFRI RIs.

An action is needed within the next HE work programme to develop and implement the data spaces concept and to understand how the diverse research products of the Science Clusters will populate these data spaces. Although the European Commission is expecting diverse stakeholders committing to data spaces, the scientific communities engaged in the construction and operation of next generation ESFRI facilities need a dedicated support to be part of a more global and resilient plan in Europe. The need to combine science, economy, technology and society through effective visions and programmatic actions is crucial. Open Science and Open Innovation today implies unifying forward-looking approaches for any ESFRI facility integrating scientific needs, key-enabling technology advancement, socio-economic impact optimization, environmental impact minimization, energy and other resources management and industrial cooperation. Such an approach needs multi-domain data and will imply the generation of a large spectrum of digital objects populating the main European Data Spaces. A cluster-platform will guarantee the cross-border environment for addressing all these societal challenges. The cluster programmes can also support such developments in regional and Member State levels, bringing the EOSC and ESFRI products closer to the user communities, and increase the applicability to smaller national infrastructures, observatories, and research performing organisations.

4. Develop the sustainability model for the EOSC science communities; foresee a model for sustainable operation that makes use of the research infrastructures to run sustainable services in the EOSC.
 - Develop a sustainable business model for the EOSC and the research infrastructures participation therein
 - Involve research infrastructures and funding agencies in defining the procurement model as part of a sustainable business case, using experience from the current EOSC Future procurement action to guide the model.
 - Develop a mechanism by which computing and storage resources are made available to general scientific users (outside of the research infrastructure-specific resource pools).
 - Support the implementation of a framework and a policy for rewarding scientists committed to Open Science.

An action where Science Clusters collaborate with the EOSC Association towards the above impact is needed.